

Art & Oceans

PartArt4OW

Funded by
the European Union

Innovate
UK

Art & Oceans

PartArt4OW

Project Management Plan

Deliverable 1.1

Funded by
the European Union

2021
2030
United Nations Decade
of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development

Innovate
UK

Authors: Chiara Certomà, Luca Bertocci, Caterina Pozzobon (UniRoma1)

Reviewed by: Antonella Passani (T6 - Ecosystems)

Funded by
the European Union

2021
2030
United Nations Decade
of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development

Innovate
UK

Table of contents

A. SUMMARY.....	6
B. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS.....	6
1. INTRODUCTION & PROJECT SUMMARY.....	7
1.1 Purpose and updates.....	7
1.2 Project summary.....	7
2. LEGAL DOCUMENTS & AGREEMENTS.....	9
2.1 Grant Agreement.....	9
2.2 Consortium Agreement.....	10
3. PROJECT ORGANISATION.....	10
3.1 Coordinator.....	10
3.1.1 Roles & Responsibilities.....	10
3.2 General Assembly (GAS).....	11
3.2.1 Roles & Responsibilities.....	11
3.3 Work Package Leaders.....	12
3.3.1 Roles & Responsibilities.....	12
3.4 Task Leaders.....	13
3.4.1 Roles & Responsibilities.....	13
3.5 Ambassador Network.....	14
4. COMMUNICATION AND COLLABORATION.....	15
4.1 Means of internal communication.....	15
4.1.1 Email.....	15
4.1.2 General rules.....	15
4.1.3 General Assemblies.....	16
4.1.4 Project Meetings.....	16
4.2 Means of external communication.....	16
4.2.1 Communication Plan.....	16
4.2.2 Roles & Responsibilities.....	17
4.2.3 Website.....	17
4.2.4 Newsletter.....	18

4.2.5 Social Media.....	18
4.2.6 File Sharing.....	18
5. PROJECT WORK PLAN & IMPLEMENTATION.....	18
5.1 Work Plan.....	18
5.2 Work Packages, Milestones and Deliverables.....	19
5.2.1 Work Packages.....	19
5.2.2 Milestones.....	23
5.2.3 Deliverable production and review.....	24
5.3 Internal review process.....	25
6. PROJECT MONITORING.....	26
6.1. Definition of responsibilities.....	26
6.2 Internal project monitoring and reporting.....	26
6.3 Periodic and Final Reports to EC.....	27
7. CONFLICT RESOLUTION.....	28

Funded by
the European Union

2021-2030
United Nations Decade
of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development

Innovate
UK

A. SUMMARY

The purpose of the Project Management Plan is twofold. Firstly, it is a reference document for the consortium partners, containing key information for day-to-day project management and providing links to further information where necessary.

In addition, the document outlines the standard procedures that the PartArt4OW consortium will follow when delivering project reports and other deliverables. Internally agreed procedures and templates are also mentioned and outlined where relevant.

The manual will be updated as necessary. For the avoidance of doubt, the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement take precedence over this document.

B. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CA Consortium Agreement

GA Grant Agreement

EC European Commission

HE Horizon Europe

GDPR General Data Policy Regulations

DMP Data Management Plan

GAS General Assembly

WP Work Package

AN Ambassador Network

PAI Participatory Art Initiative

T Task

D Deliverable

MS Milestone

PM Person month

Funded by
the European Union

2021
2030
United Nations Decade
of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development

Innovate
UK

1. INTRODUCTION & PROJECT SUMMARY

1.1 Purpose and updates

PartArt4OW Management Plan is a guide for day-to-day collaboration, establishing clear rules for project work. It also:

- Defines roles and functions within the project structure.
- Serves as the project's reference point for effective execution and quality deliverables.
- Emphasises quality control with common templates, rules for internal document reviews, and active participation of all involved.
- Addresses quality management overseen by the Project Coordinator and its project management team.

The primary goals of the Project Management Plan are to:

- Standardise documentation, reporting, and communication across all partners.
- Ensure all partners understand how their tasks relate to others' work.
- Document project progress comprehensively.
- Foster knowledge sharing and production.
- Deliver high-quality results on time as per the Work Packages.
- Address and rectify issues promptly.

1.2 Project summary

In line with the objectives of "Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030" and the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, PartArt4OW aims to (1) strengthen the emotional attachment between society and the oceans and waters; (2) raise awareness of challenges these face; (3) develop a strong transdisciplinary and trans-European network of artistic and creative communities to protect and restore oceans and inland water; (4) support policymakers in working towards sustainable ocean and water policies. To this end, PartArt4OW focuses on participatory art and creative processes on the belief that participation can bring about a deeper engagement of people with the problem of ocean and water health by performing arts themselves. PartArt4OW supports 19 trans-sectoral and transdisciplinary-inspired artistic and creative projects (PAI – Participatory Art Initiative) to support changes towards sustainability, ocean literacy, and awareness raising to strengthen maritime resilience.

PartArt4OW will:

- Strengthen the relationship and emotional attachment between society, the oceans and waters.
- Create new connections between European citizens and their local bodies of water, by raising awareness of challenges pertaining to oceans and waters across Europe.
- Develop a strong transdisciplinary network aimed to protect and restore oceans and inland waters in Europe.

Therefore, PartArt4OW will set out to:

- Provide financial support, training and mentoring to 19 interdisciplinary, intersectoral participatory projects that directly involve citizens and local stakeholders.
- Trigger citizens' creativity and artistic inclinations by bringing them together with artistic and creative professionals.
- Connect coastal and maritime communities through the PartArt4OW Sailing Lab.
- Produce and widely circulate emotionally impactful visual documentation material about PartArt4OW initiatives.
- Organising 3 Festivals to spread PartArt4OWs message and support the replication of the supported initiatives in other locations around Europe.
- Create and support via mutual learning opportunities a large ecosystem of actors interested in increasing citizens' marine and science literacy by developing art-science initiatives.
- Matchmake events during open calls, enabling potential applicants to join forces and apply together.
- Create a community among participants of selected initiatives, through dedicated sessions during the Accelerator program.

- Establish and leverage synergies with past and ongoing European initiatives (e.g. BlueParks, S+T+ARTS, NEB, Creative Europe).

The result will be the creation of an experimental space, a sandbox, to support changes towards sustainability, ocean literacy, and awareness raising to strengthen maritime resilience. Moreover, a toolkit will be provided to offer guidance and insights from our own experience. It will enable future projects to replicate our best practices for connecting coastal and maritime communities with the open ocean and for encouraging interest in blue innovation, blue research and blue economy.

2. LEGAL DOCUMENTS & AGREEMENTS

2.1 Grant Agreement

The [European Commission Grant Agreement \(GA\)](#) for PartArt4OW has the number 101157247 and is composed of:

- Preamble
- Terms and Conditions (including Data Sheet)
- Annex 1: Description of the action
- Annex 2: Estimated budget for the action
- Annex 2a: Additional information on unit costs and contributions
- Annex 3: Accession forms
- Annex 3a: Declaration on joint and several liability of affiliated entities
- Annex 4: Model for the financial statements
- Annex 5: Specific rules

The [AGA — Annotated Grant Agreement](#) is a user guide that aims to explain to applicants and beneficiaries the EU Model Grant Agreements. The purpose of this document is to help users understand and interpret their Grant Agreements (GAs). By avoiding technical vocabulary, legal references and jargon, it seeks to help readers find answers to the practical questions they may come across when setting-up or implementing their projects.

2.2 Consortium Agreement

The [PartArt4OW Consortium Agreement \(CA\)](#) was negotiated and signed by all partners. It regulates the:

- Responsibility of the parties
- Liability towards each other
- Governance structure
- Financial provisions
- Results
- Access rights
- Non-disclosure of information

The CA (and its amendments signed in May 2024) came into force with the start of the project on 01.09.2024 simultaneously. It specifies binding commitments amongst all partners, in addition to the provisions of the EC-GA. Further amendments and changes need to be done in writing.

3. PROJECT ORGANISATION

This section sets out the key roles, organisational bodies and functions, plus decision-making mechanisms adopted by the consortium.

3.1 Coordinator

3.1.1 Roles & Responsibilities

UNIRM1 – The University of Rome “La Sapienza” (Italy) - is the project Coordinator and will oversee the whole project by:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations under this Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement
- keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available

- collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certification) and specific requested documents to the Granting Authority
- preparing the meetings, proposing decisions and preparing the agenda of General Meetings, chairing the meetings, preparing the minutes of the meetings and monitoring the implementation of decisions taken at meetings
- transmitting promptly documents and information connected with the Project to any other Party concerned
- administering the financial contribution of the Granting Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks
- providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims.
- Monitoring the project objectives to ensure a smooth implementation of all activities

3.2 General Assembly (GAS)

3.2.1 Roles & Responsibilities

The General Assembly (GAS) consists of one Project Representative for each partner. It will be held three times face-to-face (during demo-days) or online whenever necessary. Each partner selects a representative that will participate in the GA. He/she will have the right to deliberate, negotiate and decide on behalf of the partner organisation he/she represents on all matters listed in Section 6.3.7 of the CA.

In the Consortium Agreement, all parties who signed the CA have agreed to abide by all decisions of the General Assembly. Each member is responsible for implementing the project within its own institution and for using in a responsible way the resource allocated to it as agreed in the DoA. The Coordinator chairs all General Assembly meetings, unless otherwise decided by the General Assembly. The General Assembly is responsible for making overall decisions and is the final decision-making body for the following:

The General Assembly is responsible for the following:

- Content, finances and intellectual property rights

- Evolution of the consortium
- Breach, defaulting party status and litigation

This includes approval of contract amendments, approval of accession of new beneficiaries or dismissal of defaulting beneficiaries, changes to the Consortium Agreement, resolution of disputes before they are referred to external arbitration or legal processes, agreeing on the plan for using and disseminating the knowledge. Details are regulated in 6.3.7 of the CA.

Decisions and agreements in the General Assembly are taken by consensus, with a two-thirds (2/3) majority vote required if consensus cannot be reached.

Beside GAS meetings, any decision may also be taken without a meeting if:

- the Coordinator circulates (by email) to all Members of the General Assembly a suggested decision with a deadline for responses and
- the decision is agreed by 51 % of all Parties

3.3 Work Package Leaders

3.3.1 Roles & Responsibilities

Each WP has a WP Leader who coordinates and is responsible for the completion and delivery of the deliverables. The WP Leaders are responsible for managing and supervising the work carried out in the Work Packages, reporting on the progress of the work and ensuring the flow of information to the other WPs. All WP Leaders are required to collect and share relevant information at the General Assembly.

The following table identifies the PartArt4OW Work Packages and their respective Leaders:

Work Packages (WP)				
WP	WP Title	WP Leader	Start (month)	End (month)
1	Project coordination and management	1 - UNIRM1	M1	M30

2	PartArt4O Framework - Open calls	2 - T6ECO	M1	M23
3	PartArt4Ocean support and acceleration program	4 - EPICA	M6	M30
4	Stakeholder engagement and ecosystem building	3 - CMMI	M1	M30
5	Impact assessment	2 - T6ECO	M6	M30
6	Communication and dissemination	5 - REGNET	M1	M30
7	Ethics requirements	1 - UNIRM1	M1	M30

The WP Leader is responsible for

- Detailed technical management at WP level
- Working closely with Task Leaders and contributing partners.
- Overseeing task delivery and overall WP performance: timelines, milestones, budgets, human resources, internal reports (see Section 7 of this Plan), deliverables.
- Ensure information flow between WPs for timely and effective coordinated work at project level.

3.4 Task Leaders

3.4.1 Roles & Responsibilities

Each WP is overseen by a WP Leader which is responsible for managing the work on each task. The following table identifies the PartArt4OW tasks and their respective leaders. Please refer to the table below for more information.

Tasks				
Number	Task Title	Lead	Start	End
T1.1	Project Coordination and management	UNIRM1	MO1	M30
T1.2	Quality assessment, ethics/data and risk management	UNIRM1	MO1	M30
T1.3	Open call administration	UNIRM1	MO1	M30

T2.1	Call definition and documentation	T6	M01	M18
T2.2	Applicant support	T6	M05	M20
T2.3	Applicant selection	T6	M06	M23
T2.4	Call statistics	T6	M06	M23
T3.1	PartArt4OW science-art ideation and conceptualization support programme	EPICA	M06	M24
T3.2	PartArt4OW implementation, exploitation and sustainability support programme	EPICA	M15	M26
T3.3	PartArt4OW Festival	EPICA	M17	M30
T3.4	PartArt4OW tracking and monitoring support programme	UNIRM1	M06	M30
T4.1	Stakeholder mapping and development of the Ambassador Network	CMMI	M01	M06
T4.2	Mutual learning exercise	CMMI	M06	M24
T4.3	Toolkit and lessons learned	UNIRM1	M20	M30
T5.1	PartArt4OW impact assessment methodology development	T6	M01	M12
T5.2	PartArt4OW impact dashboard design and development	T6	M12	M30
T5.3	Assessing the impact of PAIs and PartArt4OW as a whole	T6	M12	M30
T5.4	Sustainability and exploitation	REGNET	M06	M30
T6.1	Communication and Dissemination Plan	REGNET	M01	M06
T6.2	Branding, Website & Social Networks	REGNET	M01	M30
T6.3	Public communications and events	REGNET	M01	M30
T6.4	PartArt4OW Sailing Lab	Raw-News	M15	M30
T7.1	Ethics requirements	UNIRM1	M01	M30

3.5 Ambassador Network

A more precise definition of the nature and specific tasks of the AN will be defined throughout WP4. Generally speaking it will support the project in:

- designing the open call challenges and selection criteria.

- enriching the stakeholder mapping.
- disseminate the project open calls and the results of the PAIs.
- act as experts in the mutual learning exercise.

Moving from the EU4Ocean platform and the deep engagement of project partners in the scientific, artistic and creative sector and citizen science communities an initial map of stakeholders will be developed (WP4). Existing research activities, projects and initiatives in Europe combining art, science and participation for the Ocean and water will be mapped using FirstLife, a geolocated civic social network developed open access and open source by the University of Turin. Additional stakeholders are identified through a snowball technique.

4. COMMUNICATION AND COLLABORATION

This section deals with both internal and external communication.

4.1 Means of internal communication

4.1.1 Email

PartArt4OW partners will communicate mainly via emails. In order to facilitate the communication flow, a set of mailing-lists have been created:

- A general one, which is called PartArt4OW, where general information, issues and requests circulate.
- Six specific mailing-lists for as many WPs. These are thematic ones, where information, issues and requests circulate concerning the respective WP.

All partners have nominated persons for the different consortium-internal roles. This way, we ensure that all relevant figures within the consortium receive the information and no one is left out in the communication. If a person needs to be added/removed from the list, then each partner should request changes to the lists by sending a message to the Coordinator.

Participating researchers are encouraged to refer to their role in the PartArt4OW project in the footer of emails.

4.1.2 General rules

Any request to the EC services will be handled by the coordinator. At the technical/scientific level, the WP leaders are the link between the individual partners

and the coordinator. At the administrative level, each partner will communicate directly with the coordinator.

The following general rules apply to the communication at all levels and in all aspects of the project.

- Don't shout! Writing in all caps is generally considered to be the equivalent of shouting or yelling. It is considered bad etiquette to write in all caps unless it is used for specific purposes, such as acronyms.
- Stay tuned! All relevant information and research data will be documented and archived via the PartArt4OW website, internally-shared G-Drive folders, and Zenodo - the EU publicly available cloud service.
- Keep track! We are committed to documenting all external communication activities and include them in regular reporting.
- The website will use an inclusive, non-discriminatory and easy language to make it accessible also to people affected by different disabilities.

4.1.3 General Assemblies

The General Assembly will be attended by at least one Project Representative for each partner. It will be held three times face-to-face in Barcelona during the Demo days. These are key in-person events organized by the Consortium to allow each cohort of PAIs to show their work. During demo-days, also a project meeting will take place.

4.1.4 Project Meetings

Project Meetings will be held online on a regular basis. The first one has been held on September 3, 2024.

4.2 Means of external communication

4.2.1 Communication Plan

The Communication Plan (D6.1) pertains to the WP6 and is up to RegNet with the specific contribution of Raw-News and the participation of all partners. It develops and manages all the dissemination and communication activities of the project in order to:

- Increase awareness of the general public on ocean and water-related issues

Funded by
the European Union

2021
2030
United Nations Decade
of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development

Innovate
UK

- Maximise participation to the open calls and assure diversity of participants
- Disseminate PAIs and project activities and results
- Raise awareness on the impact and value of multidisciplinary and multisectoral collaborations for tackling ocean and water issues
- Engage and connect citizen and communities
- Briefing on the communication strategy and its dependencies.

4.2.2 Roles & Responsibilities

The Leading Partner (RegNet) is responsible for exchanging information on the progress of communication activities within and outside the PartArt4OW project. It will have three main tasks:

- To deliver the Communication and Dissemination plan, which defines the responsible partner for creating/conducting the activity, the completion date once concluded, and key performance Indicators (KPI) used to assess the reach, completeness, or success of the activity.
- To develop the project graphic identity by coordinating the creation and managing of the project's website, PartArt4OW's social media accounts and other communication channels such as social media campaigns.
- To coordinate the communication of project activities and news in mainstream media with journal articles and press releases.

The contributing partner (Raw-News) will have the main task to:

- Contribute to deliver the Communication and Dissemination plan
- To provide the audiovisual content of PartArt4OW's social media accounts and support its spread.
- To coordinate the sailing boat (Sailing Lab) expedition in accordance with UniRm1.

4.2.3 Website

The main external communication channel for PartArt4OW is the project website. It is created and managed by RegNet as coordinator and leader of the Communication and Dissemination work package (WP6). The website will be continuously updated

Funded by
the European Union

2021
2030
United Nations Decade
of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development

Innovate
UK

with news, publications, events and relevant information about the project. It will include a blog with weekly posts about the progress of the project and specific PAIs. An impact dashboard is also part of the project website. It is updated at the end of each acceleration cycle to visualise the impacts of PartArt4OW and of the PAIs.

4.2.4 Newsletter

PartArt4OW offers a quarterly newsletter with articles showcasing the progress and results of the project and of the PAIs.

4.2.5 Social Media

The project will be provided with Instagram, Facebook, Twitter/X and LinkedIn accounts. A list of related hashtags will be shared with all project participants to tag relevant social media posts.

4.2.6 File Sharing

All documents, reports, shared and standardised templates for deliverable are internally collected in a Google-drive called PartArt4OW. It is organised through main folders and sub-folders.

All data, outputs, relevant materials, documents and publications will be publicly available on Zenodo.

5. PROJECT WORK PLAN & IMPLEMENTATION

5.1 Work Plan

The following table shows the work plan of PartArt4OW's. Moreover, an excel sheet called "Implementation Plan PartArt4OW" has been created and internally shared on the google drive. It visualises all the deadlines of the project, together with WPs, Deliverables, and Tasks Leaders.

Funded by
the European Union

Innovate
UK

5.2 Work Packages, Milestones and Deliverables

5.2.1 Work Packages

Below is a summarised description of the Work Packages.

Funded by the European Union

Innovate UK

WPI. Project Coordination and Management

WP2. PartArt4OW
Framework - Open calls

WP3. PartArt4OW
support and
Accelerator program

WP4. Stakeholders
engagement and
ecosystem building

WP5. Impact Assessment

WP6. Communication and Dissemination

WP1: Project coordination and management (Lead - UNIRM1)

Tasks

- 1.1: Project Coordination and management (M1-M30; Lead: UniRm1. Participant: all).
- 1.2: Quality assessment, ethics/data and risk management (M1-30; Lead: UniRm1. Participant: all).
- 1.3: Open call administration (M1-M30; Lead: UniRm1. Participant: all).

WP2: PartArt4O Framework - Open calls (Lead: T6)

Tasks

- 2.1: Call definition and documentation (M1-18; Lead: T6. Participants: UniRm1; CMMI, EPICA).
- 2.2: Applicant support (M5-20; Lead: T6. Participants: UniRm1).

- 2.3: Applicant selection (M6-23; Lead: T6. Participants: UniRM1, CMMI, EPICA, RegNet).
- 2.4: Call statistics (M 6-23; Lead: T6. Participants: RegNet). This task collates and publishes call-related data in the form of infographics on the project website.

WP3: PartArt4Ocean support and acceleration program (Lead: EPICA)

Tasks

- 3.1: PartArt4OW science-art ideation and conceptualization support programme (M6-M24; Lead: EPICA. Participants: all).
- 3.2: PartArt4OW implementation, exploitation and sustainability support programme (M15-M26; Lead: EPICA. Participants: T6, CMMI).
- 3.3: PartArt4OW Festival (M17-M30; Lead: EPICA. Participant: all).
- 3.4: PartArt4OW tracking and monitoring support programme (M6-M30; Lead: UniRm1. Participants: T6).
- WP4: Stakeholder engagement and ecosystem building (Lead: CMMI).

WP4: Stakeholder engagement and ecosystem building (Lead: CMMI)

Tasks

- 4.1: Stakeholder mapping and development of the Ambassador Network (M1-M6, Lead: CMMI. Participants: UniRm1, T6, EPICA, RegNetT6, EPICA, RegNet)
- 4.2: Mutual learning exercise (M6-24, Lead:CMMI. Participants:UniRm1, T6, EPICA, RegNet).
- 4.3: Toolkit and lessons learned (M20-M30, Lead: UniRm1. Participants: CMMI, T6, EPICA, RegNet).

WP5: Impact assessment (Lead: T6)

Tasks

- 5.1: PartArt4OW impact assessment methodology development (M1-12. Lead: T6; Participants: UniRm1, EPICA, CMMI).
- 5.2: PartArt4OW impact dashboard design and development (M12-M30. Lead: T6. Participants:CMMI).
- 5.3: Assessing the impact of PAIs and PartArt4OW as a whole (M12-M30;Lead: T6; Participants:UniRm1, CMMI).
- 5.4: Sustainability and exploitation (M6-M30, Lead: RegNet. Participating: T6).

WP6: Communication and dissemination (Lead: RegNet)

Tasks:

- 6.1: Communication and Dissemination Plan [Lead: RegNet; Contributors: Raw-News; M1-6].
- 6.2: Branding, Website & Social Networks [M1-30; Lead: RegNet; Participants: all].
- 6.3: Public communications and events [M1-30; Lead: RegNet;Participants: all].
- 6.4: PartArt4OW Sailing Lab [M15-M30; Lead: Raw-News; Participant: RegNet].

WP7: Ethics requirements (Lead: UNIRM1)

Task:

- To appoint an Ethical Advisor.

5.2.2 Milestones

The table below outlines the Milestones of PartArt4OW.

Milestones					
Milestone n°	Milestone name	WP n°	Lead beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date (month)
1	First open call launched	WP2	2 - T6ECO	Call and related documentation published on project website	6
2	Accelerator round 1 starts	WP3	4 - EPICA	PAIs on boarded	13
3	Second open call launched	WP1	1 - UNIRM1	Call and related documentation published on project website	12
4	Pan-European survey concluded	WP4	3 - CMMI	Data cleaned and validated	14
5	Third open call	WP2	2 - T6ECO	Call and related documentation published on project website	15
6	Accelerator round 2 started	WP3	4 - EPICA	PAIs on boarded	18
7	Mutual learning exercise started	WP4	3 - CMMI	Invitation sent to stakeholders	18
8	Impact dashboard	WP5	2 - T6ECO	Dashboard published on project website	20
9	Accelerator round 3 started	WP3	4 - EPICA	PAIs on boarded	23

5.2.3 Deliverable production and review

Below is a table with due Deliverables for PartArt4OW.

Deliverables						
Deliverable n°	Deliverable name	WP n°	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
D1.1	Project management plan	WP1	1 - UNIRM1	R - Document, report	PU - Public	2
D1.2	Data management plan	WP1	1 - UNIRM1	DMP - Data Management Plan	PU - Public	6
D2.1	Open Call report 1	WP2	2 - T6ECO	R - Document, report	PU - Public	14
D2.2	Open Call report 2	WP2	2 - T6ECO	R - Document, report	PU - Public	19
D2.3	Open Call report 3	WP2	2 - T6ECO	R - Document, report	PU - Public	23
D2.4	FSTP call documentation	WP2	2 - T6ECO	R - Document, report	PU - Public	5
D3.1	Accelerator concept and training plan	WP3	4 - EPICA	R - Document, report	PU - Public	9
D3.2	Accelerator report 1	WP3	4 - EPICA	R - Document, report	PU - Public	20
D3.3	Accelerator report 2	WP3	4 - EPICA	R - Document, report	PU - Public	25
D3.4	Accelerator report 3	WP3	4 - EPICA	R - Document, report	PU - Public	25
D4.1	Interactive Stakeholder map	WP4	3 - CMMI	Other	PU - Public	6

D4.2	Report on challenges and opportunities	WP4	3 - CMMI	R - Document, report	PU - Public	24
D4.3	Interdisciplinary toolkit	WP4	3 - CMMI	R - Document, report	PU - Public	30
D5.1	PartArt4OW impact assessment methodology	WP5	2 - T6ECO	R - Document, report	PU - Public	12
D5.2	Impact assessment report	WP5	2 - T6ECO	R - Document, report	PU - Public	30
D5.3	Sustainability and exploitation plan	WP5	5 - REGNET	R - Document, report	PU - Public	30
D6.1	Communication strategy	WP6	5 - REGNET	R - Document, report	PU - Public	2
D6.2	Project website	WP6	5 - REGNET	DEC –Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	PU - Public	3
D6.3	PartArt4OW Sailing Lab expedition plan	WP6	6-Raw-News	R - Document, report	PU - Public	23
D6.4	Final report on communications activities	WP6	5 - REGNET	R - Document, report	PU - Public	30
D7.1	OEI - Requirement No. 1	WP7	1 - UNIRM1	Ethics	SEN-Sensitive	1

5.3 Internal review process

Deliverables will be reviewed internally. The process which verifies their quality and consistency and through which amendments will be suggested is organised as follows:

- A reviewer is chosen well in advance.
- The deliverable will be submitted to the designated internal reviewer one month before the EC submission deadline.

- After two weeks, he/she/they will provide feedbacks to the leading partner responsible for the deliverable.
- Subsequent two weeks are devoted to implementing amendments and final checks.

6. PROJECT MONITORING

6.1. Definition of responsibilities

It is up to the Coordinator to collect, review to verify consistency and to submit reports (M18 and M30, including financial statements). Each partner is responsible for the submission (on the portal) of its due deliverables, milestones and other specific requested documents.

6.2 Internal project monitoring and reporting

Internal project monitoring addresses three key questions:

- Do the reported effort and costs reflect the progress of the work?
- Does the remaining planned effort correspond to the remaining work to be done?
- Does the remaining budget cover the remaining work to be done?

PartArt4OW uses an integrated approach that combines:

- Internal financial status reporting (every 6 months)
- Technical Assessment of the progress of the work (every 6 months)
- An internally shared, Excel-doc with the name "Implementation Plan PartArt4OW"

In addition, project monitoring is carried out through General Assemblies and Project Meetings.

All partners will submit progress reports to the coordinator every six months. This will enable the coordinator to monitor the technical progress of the project in relation to work package plans, deliverables submission and project milestones, as well as to provide an overview of the resources committed by all partners.

Two templates have been shared on Google Drive with the Consortium to implement the internal reporting. One is about the financial effort, one concerns the activities

carried out by each partner and is to be filled in as a bullet-pointed progress description. Both templates are based on the EC model for periodic and final reports.

6.3 Periodic and Final Reports to EC

The aim of reporting is to present the work carried out, the main achievements and the use of resources. It requires the participation of the coordinator and the project leaders.

Periodic reports are a contractual obligation as defined in Article 21 of the Grant Agreement. PartArt4OW has two reporting periods: M01-18 and M19-30. Periodic reports consist of a technical and a financial part. The consortium shall submit to the Commission, within 60 days after the end of each reporting period, a periodic report for each reporting period, including:

- A technical part (to be prepared using the template available in the Portal Periodic Reporting tool) with:
 - Explanation of the work carried out
 - Overview of progress (deliverables and milestones)
 - Summary for publication
 - Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of the results.
 - Answers to the questionnaire
- A financial part with a financial statement which must contain lump sum contributions indicated in Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement, for the WPs that were completed during the reporting period.

The Final Report to the Commission (which is due within 60 days after the end of the project) shall comprise:

- A Final Technical Report:
 - Summary for publication
 - Overview of the results and their exploitation and dissemination
 - Conclusion of the action and socioeconomic impact
- A Final Financial Report:

- o Summary financial statement
- o Certificate on financial statement (if necessary).

7. CONFLICT RESOLUTION

As a general rule, the approach to project management in PartArt4OW will aim at a consensus building in order to ensure maximum cooperation within the consortium. However, in the unlikely event that a conflict arises, a majority rule approach will be adopted so that the issue may be resolved through a fair and transparent decision-making process. Decisions in General Assemblies will be taken with a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast.